

DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT DURING QUASI-STATIC AND CYCLIC LOADING IN

GRP AND CFRP LAMINATES CONTAINING 90° PLYS

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Summary

Monotonic and cyclic tension tests have been carried out on coupon test pieces cut from GRP and CFRP laminates. All the laminates were of a simple sandwich lay-up, consisting of 0° plies at the surface and 90° plies in the centre. The progress of damage was followed by using acoustic emission, optical microscopy and penetrant-enhanced X-radiography.

It was observed that transverse cracks formed in the 90° plies under monotonic tension over a wide range of strain, reaching a saturation density at a strain of about 1%. Under cyclic loading these cracks developed at lower levels of strain and accumulated during the course of the test. Crack densities similar to the saturation density under monotonic loading were reached after many cycles at strains as low as 0.35%. There was a tendency to develop a more dispersed damage pattern under the cyclic regime with more delamination and cracking of the longitudinal plies.

Introduction

The development of damage in cross-ply laminates has been extensively studied under both monotonic and cyclic loading conditions (1-5). It is generally agreed that the first significant damage under monotonic loading occurs as cracking in the transverse laminae. In tests on coupons, cracking is invariably observed to initiate at the longitudinal free edge and then to propagate across the width of the testpiece. These cracks have often been referred to as "matrix" or "resin" cracks, but it is not actually clear whether they initiate within the resin or at the fibre/matrix interface. However, observations of fracture surfaces indicate that the fracture path follows both "interface" and "resin" routes. The former exposes fibre surfaces which may be identified in the SEM. In the "resin" mode the fibres remain coated with a layer of resin. It is necessary, of course, to study *both* fracture surfaces to determine the dominant modes, and to establish whether the mode change from the *initiation* to the *propagation* stages.

The development of damage during monotonic tension loading follows a well-defined and reproducible sequence. There is a threshold value of

axial strain at which cracking commences in the transverse ply; this strain is characteristic of the particular laminate, and depends on the transverse ply thickness and, in more complex laminates, on the stacking sequence. The cracking threshold increases as the 90° ply thickness is decreased, and is influenced by the relative stiffness of adjacent plies (eg 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ orientations).

As the applied strain exceeds this cracking threshold, further cracks develop over a range of strain until an apparent saturation crack density is attained; this crack density is also found to depend on transverse ply thickness, but is apparently independent of laminate stacking sequence in the case of complex quasi-isotropic laminates. Reifsnider (6) termed this saturation cracking pattern the "characteristic damage state".

In addition to transverse ply cracking, other types of damage can occur, particularly at strains close to failure. Delamination between the longitudinal and transverse plies initiates at the free edges of the test coupon but develops to a significant extent only at high transverse ply crack densities. Tensile failure usually intervenes before this delamination can grow across the width of the coupon. Cracking parallel to the fibres in the longitudinal ply is observed at high strain levels, shortly after crack saturation in the transverse ply, and precedes the final tensile fracture of the load-bearing 0° plies.

Longitudinal ply cracking has been the subject of fewer investigations, but appears to be similar in nature to transverse cracking. The crack follows a path within the matrix rather than at the actual fibre-matrix interface, leaving a deposit of resin adhering to the surface of the fibres. Cracks invariably propagate from the gripped ends of coupons tested in monotonic tension. The ends are effectively the "free edges" in the longitudinal direction. The constraint due to the grips sets up a stress concentration which helps to initiate the cracks; these then propagate quickly along the length of the coupon, leading to further delamination and ultimately to final catastrophic failure. This final phase of failure is difficult to observe in detail because it initiates suddenly, and rapidly becomes unstable. Final failure is accompanied by much consequential damage due to the sudden release of elastic strain energy when fracture occurs.

The primary cause of the longitudinal ply cracking is the secondary tensile stress acting in the transverse direction of this ply, induced by interaction between the 0° and 90° plies. This secondary stress reaches sufficient magnitude to cause cracking only at high axial strains, which are necessarily close to the failure strain of the longitudinal ply. Hence, in contrast to transverse ply cracking, a consistent pattern of longitudinal cracking does not develop to any great extent before final fracture of the testpiece occurs.

Damage under cyclic loading conditions has also been investigated by a number of workers. Highsmith et al. (7) attempted to correlate the pattern of damage occurring under both monotonic and cyclic loading with various parameters related to the fatigue resistance of composite laminates, notably stiffness reduction. As a general observation, the damage developed under cyclic loading is at least superficially similar to that produced by monotonic loading, including transverse ply cracking, delamination and longitudinal ply cracking. Both delamination and longitudinal ply cracking are more extensive under fatigue conditions.

In the present work, we have attempted to quantify the development of damage in similar laminates under both monotonic and cyclic tension loading

conditions and to relate this damage to a reduction in axial stiffness. Extensive studies of damage morphology have also been undertaken using electron and optical microscopy and X-radiography.

Experimental

The carbon fibre reinforced material contained 0.6 V_f Courtaulds XAS fibres in Ciba-Geigy 914 epoxy resin. The GRP contained approximately 0.58 V_f E-glass in Ciba-Geigy 913 epoxy resin. Laminates of the configuration (0/90₃)_s were laid-up in both materials from 0.125 mm thick prepreg. The CFRP was cured at 170°C in an autoclave, and the GRP was cured at 120°C in a hot press. The laminates were then inspected using ultrasonic C-scan to assess the quality of the moulding before cutting out rectangular coupons measuring 230 mm by 20 mm. The edges of some coupons were polished to a metallographic standard to allow observation of damage development throughout the test using an optical microscope. Aluminium alloy end tabs and electrical resistance strain gauges were bonded to all of the coupons.

The monotonic tests were conducted in an Instron machine. The signal from the strain gauge oriented parallel to the testing direction was processed to give a record of the test in the form of load plotted against axial strain; values of strength, Young's modulus and ultimate strain could be determined from these plots. The principal Poisson's ratio could be calculated using measurements from a second strain gauge, oriented perpendicular to the testing axis. The acoustic emission count rate was monitored in some of the tests, using a centrally-positioned transducer with two guard transducers to screen out extraneous noise from the gripped ends and from the machine.

Fatigue tests were carried out in a servo-hydraulic machine, using a load control mode at a frequency of 10 Hz. The wave form was sinusoidal. Specimens were subjected to "zero-tension" cyclic loading at a constant stress ratio of $R = 0.01$. The change in axial strain during cyclic load was monitored for a limited number of coupons using a dynamic extensometer.

Several methods were used to follow the development of damage during testing:

Penetrant-enhanced X-radiography was used for those coupons which did not have pre-polished edges, and to examine for internal damage in all of the coupons. A zinc iodide solution was applied to the free edges for approximately 30 minutes, with the coupon oriented horizontally and subjected to a small tensile load to improve penetration into the damage zones. The excess solution was then wiped off, and the radiographic exposure made on ultra-fine grain X-ray film at a tube potential of 26 kV.

Coupons with pre-polished edges were observed at intervals during the test with a low-power optical photo-microscope mounted directly in front of the testing machine. They could be removed to a higher magnification optical microscope when a more detailed examination was appropriate. Sections were taken from some test pieces, after testing, for examination in the optical and scanning electron microscopes.

Several coupons from the CFRP and GRP laminates were loaded to failure in monotonic tension. Acoustic emission was also monitored to give an indication of the onset of damage, to be correlated with subsequent observations of damage at intervals during ramp-loading of the laminates.

These initial tests provided values of the laminate properties, ie modulus, strength, Poisson's ratio, and established maximum stress amplitudes for later fatigue tests. The sequence of damage development under monotonic loading was then studied by non-destructively evaluating the damage state in a single coupon at several stages. This also gave the relationship between transverse ply crack density and axial strain. The CFRP coupon was loaded in increments of strain of 0.1%, unloaded and examined by X-radiography, up to failure; the GRP coupon was examined visually at intervals during loading to failure. Microscopy of the failed coupons gave further information about the damage state.

Fatigue tests were carried out on several coupons from each laminate to study the sequence of damage at intervals during the course of cyclic loading, and to establish how the relation between transverse ply crack density and number of fatigue cycles was influenced by cyclic stress amplitude. Strain at levels were selected which were both above and below the transverse ply cracking thresholds established under monotonic loading. Since the tests were conducted under "load control", the maximum load in the cycle was set so as to produce the required levels of strain by loading the coupon monotonically to that level. The rest of the test was then under load control and the actual strain range would change in response to any change in stiffness of the test piece. Attempts were made to correlate axial stiffness reduction with fatigue damage development both by static stiffness measurements during an interrupted test, and by continuous monitoring. This was done using a 25 mm gauge length extensometer attached to the central portion of the coupon, with the knife edges located in grooves in two thin strips of epoxy adhesive placed across the coupon width, or in grooves cut into two metal tabs bonded to the surface of the coupon. Damage in these coupons was observed on the pre-polished free edge.

Results

Monotonic Tests

The stress-strain curve for the CFRP (0/90₃)₅ laminate (figure 1) is almost linear although it shows a slight increase in modulus with increasing strain. Extensive cracking at strains close to failure cause discontinuities in the curve where a sudden increase in extension may be recorded for no appreciable increase in load. The curve for the GRP laminate (figure 1) is more markedly non-linear, the modulus decreasing with increasing strain. Again there were discontinuities in the curve due to localised cracking, particularly beneath the strain gauge bonded to the coupon surface.

The strain to failure of the GRP laminate was 1.5% (average of 5 test results) and that of the CFRP was just under 1.1% (average of 4 test results). The values of failure strain, and also the strengths of the laminates, reflect the properties of the longitudinal lamina in each case. The strain to failure of a unidirectional GRP laminate is around 2% ϵ , but this is modified by the high proportion of 90° plies in the crossply laminate. The Young's moduli varied with axial strain as mentioned previously; the low strain (0.25% ϵ) moduli for the GRP and CFRP laminates were measured as 21 GPa and 41.5 GPa respectively. These values correspond closely with the moduli predicted from the unidirectional material properties by classical laminate analysis theory i.e. GRP - 23.5 GPa, CFRP - 43 GPa.

Figure 1 Stress-strain curves for $(0/90)_3$ CFRP and GRP laminates, including a simplified acoustic emission trace for the GRP laminate.

Figure 1 also shows a simplified acoustic emission count rate for the GRP laminate. The count rate was negligible until approximately 0.7%; the onset of acoustic emission at this point correlated well with the beginning of transverse ply cracking, identified by visual observation of the translucent test coupon. The transverse ply cracking threshold was reproducible in subsequent tests on different coupons. Cracking generally began at the free edge and propagated across the width of the coupon, although a few cracks were seen to initiate within the coupon away from the edge. The crack density increased with increasing axial strain until reaching saturation at approximately 1.2%. Cracks were then observed in the longitudinal ply running parallel to the fibre direction; these initiated both from inside the gripped ends and along the length of the coupon away from the ends. In contrast to the damage pattern described for the CFRP laminate in a later section, there was a relatively large range of strains between crack saturation and coupon failure over which longitudinal ply cracks developed. Final fracture in the 0° plies was influenced by the cracks in the adjacent transverse ply: the fracture generally ran normal to the 0° fibre direction and was localised at a particular site, with some delamination spreading along the length of the coupon. This could be attributed to the higher strain to failure of the glass/epoxy compared with the carbon/epoxy material, in which catastrophic failure occurs very shortly after the saturation transverse ply crack density is attained.

a. 0.5% strain

b. 0.8% strain

c. 1.05% — failed

d. 0.68% strain—1 cycle

e. 12×10^3 cycles

f. 590×10^3 cycles

Figure 2 Sequences of X-radiographs showing the development of damage in the CFRP laminates at stages during monotonic loading to failure (a-c) and fatigue loading at 0.68% (d-f).

Figure 3 Transverse ply crack density against axial strain for a CFRP coupon loaded to failure in monotonic tension.

The development of damage in the CFRP laminate was followed in a single coupon using X-radiography. The monotonic tensile test was interrupted at intervals of 0.1% strain to make an X-ray exposure, then loading continued until the coupon failed. Figure 2 shows three stages of this sequence of radiographs. The transverse ply cracking threshold was established using acoustic emission, confirmed by non-destructive examination, as approximately 0.4%. Figure 2(a) shows the radiograph taken at 0.5%; there are several transverse cracks, most of which span the whole width of the coupon, and one crack is propagating from the edge. The next stage at 0.8%, figure 2(b), is towards the end of the region of rapid increase in crack density with strain and the density is approaching the maximum. The last stage, figure 2(c), is after failure of the coupon at 1.05%. The transverse crack density has reached saturation, and damage in the longitudinal ply can be seen propagating from the gripped end of the coupon where failure occurred. There is some delamination between the 0° and 90° plies, although this is relatively localised around the fracture site. Transverse crack density against axial strain is plotted in figure 3 and the micrograph in figure 4(a) shows an area on the edge of this same coupon which was polished and examined after failure. This is typical of the damage produced under monotonic tension; cracks in the 90° ply run perpendicular to the longitudinal fibre direction, with very little delamination at the intersection of a transverse crack with the 0/90 interface. Some cracks actually appear to be arrested by a resin-rich layer at the interface. The crack spacing at saturation density is of the order of the transverse ply thickness.

Figure 4 Optical micrographs showing damage on the edge of CFRP coupons: (a) after failure in monotonic tension, (b) after 591000 fatigue cycles at 0.68% level.

Fatigue Tests

The majority of fatigue tests have been done for the CFRP laminate. Tests were conducted at levels both above and below the monotonic cracking threshold of 0.4%. Coupons were loaded statically to measured strains of 0.35%, 0.4%, 0.5%, 0.6% and 0.68%; the load corresponding to the selected strain was then collected as the maximum cyclic load in the zero-tension fatigue schedule with R set to 0.01. The test was continued up to approximately 6×10^5 cycles for the highest loading level, or up to a minimum of 10^6 cycles for all other levels. Transverse ply crack densities were measured at various intervals throughout the tests, the interval being shorter for higher loading levels.

The development of damage for the 0.68% level test is indicated in the X-radiographs in figure 2(d)-(f). This coupon did not have pre-polished edges, hence the test was stopped at intervals of 2000 cycles for radiographic examination. Figure 2(d) was taken after the initial monotonic loading to 0.68%; the initial transverse ply crack density was somewhat lower than expected from previous measurements of crack density with strain, cf. figure 3. After 12000 cycles, the crack density was approximately the same as that produced by loading to just over 0.8% in monotonic tension, figure 2(e). This stage was towards the end of the initial period of very high rate of increase in crack density which was observed at this test level (figure 5). Most of the cracks span the full width of the coupon, although the radiograph shows a few short cracks which appear to be confined to the edge region of the coupon. These cracks are not as well-defined as the primary transverse cracks, and they propagated very slowly across the width of the coupon over many thousands of cycles.

Figure 5 Transverse ply crack density against log (number of cycles) for fatigue loading of CFRP coupons at levels of 0.68%, 0.6%, 0.5%, 0.4% and 0.35% strain.

Longitudinal ply cracking was beginning at the gripped end. The test was stopped after 591,000 cycles, figure 2(f). The radiograph now shows extensive longitudinal ply cracks propagating from the ends, and throughout the length of the coupon. Delamination towards one end was evident, as a strip of the surface 0° ply had peeled away. The transverse ply crack density reached a maximum after approximately 75,000 cycles at a value just higher than the final monotonic crack density. It is expected that the saturation crack densities under fatigue and monotonic loading should be the same; the higher density measured at the end of the cyclic test may be due to the uncertainty involved in counting the short, fainter transverse cracks mentioned above. The number of these cracks increased between 12,000 and 591,000 cycles, whilst those which were present early in the test may have grown up to halfway across the coupon width and been included in the crack count.

The damage produced by monotonic and cyclic loading can be compared by referring to figure 2(c) and (f). Although the fatigue coupon had not failed after 591000 cycles, the longitudinal ply cracking and 0/90 ply delamination at this stage is much more extensive than in the fractured monotonically-loaded coupon. Fatigue damage in the longitudinal ply is not confined to the gripped ends, but short cracks are observed throughout the ply, apparently unconnected with the cracks at the ends. Saturation crack densities appear to be similar in both cases; however, only the fatigue coupon shows short transverse cracks close to the edge region between the well-defined cracks.

100µm

Figure 6 Optical micrograph of secondary angled cracking at the edge of a fatigue-loaded CFRP coupon.

Figure 7 SEM micrograph of CFRP fatigue transverse crack fracture surface; note that fibres are covered with a layer of matrix material.

Edge sections and cross-sections were taken from the fatigue coupon at various positions, and polished for examination in the optical microscope. Knowing the exact location of the section along the length of the coupon, the damage observed could be correlated with the information given by the radiograph, figure 2(f). These secondary cracks were associated with almost all of the main transverse cracks (figure 4(b); they spanned about half of 90° ply thickness and ran towards the main crack at angles between approximately 40° and 50° to the longitudinal ply. Two such angled cracks were generally observed on both sides of a main crack; these cracks intersected each other before reaching the main crack. Figure 4(b) shows some delamination at the 0/90 interface associated with the transverse crack, which was not evident after monotonic loading, figure 4(a). The angled cracks seemed to cause further delamination at the 0/90 interface, although this was apparently unconnected with the other delamination. Figure 6 also shows short cracks in the resin-rich layer separating the 90° and 0° plies. These cracks were caused by shear at the interface as the plies moved relative to each other during cyclic loading; this action was enhanced as delamination due to the main crack propagated, allowing greater relative movement of the plies. Further observations are required to determine whether there is a characteristic spacing between the main transverse cracks and the angled cracks, and how this depends on 90° ply thickness.

A section of cracked transverse ply was extracted from the fatigue coupon for examination in the scanning electron microscope. The fracture surface (figure 7) shows fibres covered with a layer of resin, which indicates that the transverse crack propagated within the matrix rather than at the actual fibre-matrix interface. This is also typical of a monotonic transverse crack in this laminate.

Fatigue tests on the CFRP laminate were also conducted at levels corresponding to initial monotonic loading to 0.6%, 0.5%, 0.4% and 0.35% strain. Plots of transverse ply crack density against number of cycles for these tests are included in figure 5.

With the exception of the test at 0.35%, the curves are ranked in accordance with the test level. They all show a similar shape, indicating an initial incubation period of several thousand cycles before a rapid increase in transverse ply crack density. Only the 0.68% curve seems to level off before 10^6 cycles. The 0.35% test coupon was the only one examined using X-radiography - the others had pre-polished edges - and although no deleterious effect of the radio-opaque penetrant has previously been observed, this should be considered when explaining the discrepancy. This test will be repeated on a coupon with polished edges.

The crack density after 10^6 cycles in the 0.6% test approached the monotonic saturation density, but the crack densities in the 0.5% and 0.4% tests at this stage were much lower. Work is currently in progress to continue fatigue loading beyond 10^6 cycles at each test level to look for eventual crack saturation and a plateau in the curve. A test at 0.2% is also being run to find out whether any transverse cracking will occur within several million cycles of very low-level loading.

Secondary angled cracks associated with the main transverse ply cracks were present at the 0.6% and 0.5% test levels after 10^6 cycles, but not at the 0.4% test. The crack density after 10^6 cycles at the 0.4% level was 0.3 mm^{-1} , whereas angled cracking began at the higher test levels only after the transverse cracking had exceeded approximately 0.45 mm^{-1} . Angled cracks initiated during the interval between observations of the 0.5% level test at 250000 cycles and 350000 cycles ie crack densities of 0.45 mm^{-1} and 0.51 mm^{-1} respectively. At the 0.6 test level, these cracks initiated between 20000 cycles and 35500 cycles, corresponding to crack densities of 0.44 mm^{-1} and 0.49 mm^{-1} . The short faint transverse cracks first appear on the X-radiograph taken at 10000 cycles for the 0.68% test; the corresponding crack density is 0.61 mm^{-1} . The cracks may have initiated earlier than 10000 cycles, but it was not possible to check this by direct observation of the edge. Preliminary data from stiffness reduction measurements during the 0.6% test indicated that stiffness began to drop as the pattern of secondary cracks developed extensively ie approximately 3.5% decrease in modulus after 750000 cycles. In the high cycle-high level tests, there was also extensive damage growing into the longitudinal ply at the coupon edge where the transverse cracks met the 0/90 interface.

Delamination at the 0/90 interface developed in all of the tests to an extent which depended on the loading level. X-radiographs showed that the delamination did not spread far across the width of the coupons but was confined to a region close to the edge of the coupon. Radiographs also showed some longitudinal ply cracking in the 0.6% and 0.5% tests after 10^6 cycles.

Fatigue damage in the GRP $(0/90_3)_S$ has not been studied as extensively as for the CFRP laminate. The types of damage produced under monotonic and cyclic loading are essentially the same. Work is in progress to measure transverse ply crack density with number of cycles at various levels. Some preliminary measurements of the reduction in stiffness during cyclic loading at the 0.58% level show a good correlation with rate of increase in crack density; the modulus begins to drop markedly as the

transverse crack density increases rapidly up to a saturation density similar to the monotonic saturation density.

Conclusions

The sequence of both static and fatigue damage development in carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy (0/90₃)₅ composite laminates has been studied in detail. The change in transverse ply crack density with either monotonic strain or number of fatigue cycles has been measured. It was observed that the crack density reaches a maximum which is characteristic of this laminate; this saturation density was attained after loading to failure in monotonic tension, and at sufficiently high cyclic tensile loads within 10⁶ cycles. Fatigue at lower loads - even loads below the threshold for transverse cracking in a static test - produced extensive cracking in tests of the same duration. The crack density attained then depended on the test level; further work should indicate whether there is a limiting value of crack density depending on the magnitude of cyclic load, or whether the saturation density is eventually reached whatever the cyclic load level. Other damage modes were also identified in the CFRP laminate. Delamination at the 0/90 interface and longitudinal ply cracking occurred in both static and fatigue loading, but was generally more severe in fatigue tests. A secondary form of transverse crack was also identified in the later stages of some fatigue tests. Preliminary measurements of stiffness reduction correlated with increasing transverse crack density in the glass/epoxy laminate.

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